

About the proper motion of lensed quasars in Gaia DR2

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Abstract

The distribution of the normalised parallaxes and proper motions of Gaia DR2 quasars follows nicely a Gaussian distribution with standard deviation close to 1. One would naively expect that the subset of lensed QSOs has the same property. We propose 2 different Bayesian statistical models to compare the proper motion distributions of the non-lensed QSOs and lensed QSOs subsets. We conclude that these 2 distributions are different. Finally we discuss different hypotheses to explain this discrepancy. In particular one should always keep in mind that DR2 astrometry is biased for objects that are not isolated within a few arcseconds because of blended astrometric observations. The lensed QSOs potentially illustrate such biases.

1 Introduction

The second Gaia data release (DR2) [Gaia Collaboration et al. \(2016, 2018\)](#) has been successfully exploited to identify lensed quasars (LQSO) candidates¹, in a standalone mode or combining it with external catalogue as done in [Ducourant, C. et al. \(2018\)](#); [Lemon et al. \(2018\)](#). In both papers the authors noted that the distribution of Gaia proper motion for the lensed quasar components is different than the one of the quasar. In particular one should not apply a too strong proper motion cut in order to not exclude LQSOs. The day DR2 was published we explored the proper motion of the QSOs and of the known LQSOs images and we noticed that a large fraction of the proper motion of LQSOs components deviate from zero by more than 3 standard deviations.

Both the apparent proper motion of QSOs and LQSOs, if measurable, contain physical information. Can it be that the LQSOs proper motion contain physical information that is not detectable for non-lensed QSOs? The global pattern of QSOs has been established as a tool to constrain the galactic acceleration and the power of gravitational waves from the CMB. The errors in DR2 are still too large to allow any characterisation of these 2 patterns [Mignard, F. et al. \(2018\)](#). Moreover some models predict that the optical centroid part of QSO might have proper motion of the order of 10 to 100 $\mu\text{as/yr}$, one order of magnitude smaller than their expected formal error [Bachchan, R. K. et al. \(2016\)](#). One might then expect it to be large enough to be measured once magnified by a gravitational lens. We traced back the idea of exploiting proper motion in gravitational lensed QSO to [Kochanek et al. \(1996\)](#). The authors argue that *by measuring the dipole of the proper motions in an ensemble of lenses we can set limits on the deviation of the inertial frame defined by the lenses from that defined by the CMB dipole and estimate the Hubble con-*

stant. Will this ever be possible with Gaia data? In [Jin et al. \(2003\)](#) the authors study the angular separation between the 2 components of lensed quasar PKS 1830-211 using 8 VLBA observations and the evolution of the structure of both components. Transposing this study to Gaia observations, one might expect to have perturbation of the proper motion in the direction of the jet.

2 Distribution comparison

2.1 Proper motion

Let $(\mu_{\alpha^*}, \mu_{\delta})$ the proper motion of a Gaia source [Lindgren, L. et al. \(2018\)](#). In order to quantify the significance of the proper motion among the strong lensed QSO images, we use the norm of the proper motion

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} = \begin{pmatrix} \mu_{\alpha^*} \\ \mu_{\delta} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

with the error taking in account the correlation between the right ascension and declination proper motion errors.

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{\mu_{\alpha^*}}^2 & \sigma_{\mu_{\alpha^*}} \sigma_{\mu_{\delta}} \\ \sigma_{\mu_{\alpha^*}} \sigma_{\mu_{\delta}} & \sigma_{\mu_{\delta}}^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

Following [Mignard, F. et al. \(2018\)](#) we use the largest eigenvalue of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ as the formal error of norm of the proper motion $\mu = |\boldsymbol{\mu}|$.

2.2 Data

The data was extracted from the Gaia archive using ADQL queries. In appendix we outline the queries used to extract the data.

For the lensed quasar sample we use the CfA-Arizona Space Telescope LEns Survey of gravitational lenses² (CASTLeS survey). We do a cone search of $5''$ around their position and remove manually the objects with potentially star contaminants.

¹There is a real interest in finding out all the lensed QSOs in Gaia's catalog. For example, the distribution of LQSO, such as the number of LQSO as a function of redshift, is a also probe of the matter density between the QSOs and us, and hence can be use in principle to constrain cosmological models [Finet & Surdej \(2016\)](#).

²<https://www.cfa.harvard.edu/castles/>

Figure 1: Marginal density distribution of the log proper motion for the 2 data sets, QSO (solid) and LQSO (dashed).

Figure 2: Marginal density distributions of the QSO and LQSO datasets in magnitude and normalised proper motion space.

For the quasar sample we use the selection of ALLWISE quasar flagged as frame rotator object. We do a cone search of $5''$ around their position and removed possible non isolated objects by rejecting the one with a companion and known lensed quasars from the CASTLeS catalog. We are aware that the Castles survey and our quasar selection are not the most complete but they are sufficient for the present discussion. In the following we call them LQSO and QSO datasets. After filtering the LQSO dataset contains 115 Gaia DR2 sources whereas the QSO dataset contains 466044 sources. In [Figure 1](#) we plot the density distribution of the log proper motion for these 2 datasets.

If we restrict this simple study to only the proper motion, these distributions are multi dimensional. In particular there is some magnitude dependency. In [Figure 2](#) we plot the marginal density estimate of the proper motion over error versus magnitude for both dataset.

2.3 Model1

In model 1 we restrict the analysis to the norm of the proper motion vector μ . The quasar proper motions can be described by a log normal distribution [Figure 1](#). We fit a Bayesian hierarchical model to find the underlying distribu-

Figure 3: Model 1. Corner plot of the samples of population parameters. The dotted lines show the 0.16, 0.5, 0.84 quantiles.

tions for the lensed and non-lensed quasars assuming a log normal shape.

We are looking for the posterior distribution

$$P(\mu_1, \mu_2, \sigma_1, \sigma_2 | \hat{\mu}_q, \hat{\mu}_l, \sigma_{\mu_q}, \sigma_{\mu_l}) \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{\mu}_q, \hat{\mu}_l$ are the observed proper motions and $\mu_1, \mu_2, \sigma_1, \sigma_2$ are the means and standard deviations of the population distribution for the quasar and lenses respectively.

We introduce the true proper motions μ_q, μ_l and decompose the likelihood in 4 factors

$$P(\mu_q | \mu_1, \sigma_1) P(\mu_l | \mu_2, \sigma_2) \quad (4)$$

$$P(\hat{\mu}_q | \mu_q, \sigma_{\mu_q}) P(\hat{\mu}_l | \mu_l, \sigma_{\mu_l}) \quad (5)$$

with

$$P(\mu_q | \mu_1, \sigma_1) = \mathcal{LN}(\mu_1, \sigma_1) \quad (6)$$

$$P(\mu_l | \mu_2, \sigma_2) = \mathcal{LN}(\mu_2, \sigma_2) \quad (7)$$

$$P(\hat{\mu}_q | \mu_q, \sigma_{\mu_q}) = \mathcal{N}(\mu_q, \sigma_{\mu_q}) \quad (8)$$

$$P(\hat{\mu}_l | \mu_l, \sigma_{\mu_l}) = \mathcal{N}(\mu_l, \sigma_{\mu_l}) \quad (9)$$

and we use the priors

$$\mu_1, \mu_2, \sigma_1, \sigma_2 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1). \quad (10)$$

In total the number of parameters in the model is driven by the size of the LQSO dataset and the 4 population parameters [Figure 3](#). The median of the QSO sample is -0.7 and the mean of the LQSO sample is -0.3. A summary of statistical information of the samples of population parameters are available in [Table 1](#).

	μ_1	μ_2	σ_1	σ_2
Q16	-0.74	-0.46	0.35	1.08
Q50	-0.70	-0.33	0.38	1.16
Q84	-0.65	-0.12	0.44	1.34
std	0.04	0.17	0.04	0.14

Table 1: Model 1 summary

Figure 4: Model 2. Corner plot of the samples of QSO parameters. The dotted lines show the 0.16, 0.5, 0.84 quantiles.

Figure 5: Model 2. Corner plot of the samples of LQSO parameters. The dotted lines show the 0.16, 0.5, 0.84 quantiles.

2.4 Model2

In model 2 we use the full *Gaia* likelihood for the proper motion as introduced in Section 2.1. Using the same indices notation than in model 1 but considering the proper motion vectors $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ instead of their norm μ . Taking in account that the model is more complex we restrict the study to a random sample of the QSO with the same size of the LQSO.

The likelihood of the model

$$P(\boldsymbol{\mu}_1, \boldsymbol{\mu}_2, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_2 | \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_q, \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_l, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\boldsymbol{\mu}_q}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\boldsymbol{\mu}_l}) \quad (11)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_q$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_l$ are the observed proper motions $\boldsymbol{\mu}_q$, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_l$ are the true proper motions and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_1$, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_2$, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_1$, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_2$ are the means and standard deviations of the population distribution for the quasar and lenses respectively.

Instead of assuming log normal distributions for the norm of the proper motion vectors, we use multi-normal distributions,

$$P(\boldsymbol{\mu}_q | \boldsymbol{\mu}_1, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1) = \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_1, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1) \quad (12)$$

$$P(\boldsymbol{\mu}_l | \boldsymbol{\mu}_2, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_2) = \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_2, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_2) \quad (13)$$

$$P(\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_q | \boldsymbol{\mu}_q, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\boldsymbol{\mu}_q}) = \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_q, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\boldsymbol{\mu}_q}) \quad (14)$$

$$P(\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_l | \boldsymbol{\mu}_l, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\boldsymbol{\mu}_l}) = \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_l, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\boldsymbol{\mu}_l}) \quad (15)$$

Corner plots of samples of parameters population are available on Figure 4 and Figure 5 and statistical summary in Table 2 and Table 3 for respectively QSO and LQSO sam-

	μ_r	μ_d	σ_r	σ_d
Q16	-0.04	-0.07	0.10	0.05
Q50	-0.00	-0.03	0.16	0.09
Q84	0.07	0.03	0.26	0.20
std	0.06	0.05	0.08	0.08

Table 2: Model 2 summary for QSO

	μ_r	μ_d	σ_r	σ_d
Q16	-0.32	-0.59	0.85	1.66
Q50	-0.23	-0.45	0.94	1.79
Q84	-0.08	-0.19	1.09	2.02
std	0.12	0.21	0.12	0.18

Table 3: Model 2 summary for LQSO

ples.

3 Conclusion

In the previous section we demonstrate that the proper motion of lensed QSOs deviate from zero by an amount that cannot presently be explained by their formal errors. Is it a physical signal or a marker of biases in DR2? With the present available data it is challenging to drive any conclusion. In particular one should take in account that QSOs are potentially extended objects. Moreover being magnified by a foreground galaxy each lensed QSO presents multiple components within a few arcseconds. Some internal DPAC studies have demonstrated that the current astrometric observations (i.e. the transit times) can be strongly biased for close paired sources up to a separation of a few arcsecond and create astrometric bias. One might think of the problem of fitting a bimodal distribution with a single Gaussian. The biases are complex and depend mostly on the angular separation between the sources, their magnitude difference and the scanning law. The lensed QSOs are a good example of sources with potentially biased astrometric solution in Gaia DR2. Ideally one should look to each Gaia observations and take in account all possible biases when computing the centroids. Hence only a data release with epoch raw observations will eventually provide enough information to not only detect but study the lensed QSOs observed with Gaia.

There are millions of sources that are very likely affected by such biases. Any user of Gaia DR2 should question the validity of the model used by DPAC. If blended PSF is a well known issue for photometry it is not so well documented for astrometry. Indeed all the DR2 processing was done with a single source model. Not only the astrometric solution used a single source 5 parameters model, but also the image parameter determination was done assuming isolated sources. Hopefully the problem will be mitigated in further data releases but some additional effort might be needed to squeeze the data.

Gaia archive ADQL queries

The frame rotator sources, used here as QSOs sample, are directly available in the archive.

Listing 1: Rough selection of qso_allwise

```
SELECT * FROM gaiadr2.gaia_source WHERE
frame_rotator_object_type = 3
```

The CASTLeS sources listed on a webpage should be transformed to a csv and then uploaded as a user table *lensed_qso* before doing a 5" cone search around them.

Listing 2: 5" cone search around lensed_qso

```
SELECT lqso.source_id AS qso_id, gaia.*
FROM gaiadr2.gaia_source AS gaia,
user_XXX.lensed_qso AS lqso
WHERE 1=CONTAINS(
POINT('ICRS', lqso.ra, lqso.dec),
CIRCLE('ICRS', gaia.ra, gaia.dec,
0.08333333))
```

Code

The plots and data analysis presented in this letter are available in the project GaiaLQSO on GitHub.³

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³In particular the following notebook provides all the code used to produced them https://github.com/Bombrun/GaiaLQSO/blob/master/notebooks/ESALB53/Compare_distributions.ipynb.